

AN ALTERNATIVE METHOD FOR ADVANCING GLASS TRANSITION TEMPERATURE IN EPOXY BASED COMPOSITES FOR SOFTENING SENSITIVE MEASUREMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Components manufactured from composite materials undergo multiple processes to transform raw materials into final structures. Properly characterizing the incoming raw materials has been a challenge due to their low mechanical properties. This paper documents a procedure for advancing the glass transition temperature, thus increasing mechanical properties, of epoxy based preregs by allowing aqueous ammonium hydroxide to diffuse the resin internal structure and react with the epoxides, all at room temperature. The impact of the ammonium hydroxide soak on cure shrinkage is documented and a fibre misalignment case study on the application of this process is presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

The quality of incoming materials is important for composite part manufacturing. Poor knowledge and control over incoming factors such as fibre alignment, porosity, thickness, tack, and other properties feeds variability in final composite parts [1]. This leads to risk, less efficient designs, non-destructive testing, or some combination thereof, which all increase cost.

For thermoset preregs, accurately measuring incoming quality is difficult due to the relatively soft properties of the matrix with many characterization techniques relying on sectioned microscopy of stiff materials [2, 3]. Modifying these existing techniques for application towards soft composite materials remains a challenge [4]. Traditionally, in preparation for microscopy, thermosets are run through a cure cycle but this inherently modifies the state of the fibres, matrix, void location and content, and so forth. The shear modulus of a resin (of interest to this work Hexcel 8552-1) decreases by several orders of magnitude during the heating ramp of a thermal cure cycle [5, 6]. Also, single carbon fibres have been shown to buckle and misalign, caused by cure shrinkage occurring during a cure cycle [7]. Therefore, any investigation into pre-cure values which are dependent on resin modulus and cure shrinkage must be carefully interpreted from post-cure characterization.

Like many other resin systems used in the aerospace industry, the exact chemical composition of Hexcel's 8552-1 is proprietary and is unknown to the end users. However, a variant with a slightly different catalyst, Hexcel's 8552, has been studied extensively in the literature and its chemical composition, Figure 1, has been documented as a stoichiometrically epoxy-rich tetraglycidyl 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane, (TGDDM), premixed with an amine curing agent 4,4'-diaminodiphenylsulfone, (DDS), [8, 9]. A full description of the reaction pathways can be found in the literature [10] and is beyond the scope of this work, however, a brief description of the main pathway and reactants is warranted. During a traditional thermal cure cycle, primary amines, DDS, react with epoxides, TGDDM, to form secondary amines. These secondary amines can go on to react with other primary amines to complete the reaction and form tertiary amines. With three, or more, functional groups, the compound can form expansive 3-dimensional networks from this primary-secondary-tertiary reaction path.

Figure 1: a) Tetraglycidyl-4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (TGDDM) b) 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl sulfone (DDS)

At room temperature, the DDS-epoxy reaction is extremely slow [11]; alternative strategies are required to advance cure without increasing the resin temperature. These strategies include electron-beam-curing epoxies and micro-computer tomography (μ CT). However, e-beam curing epoxies can require several minutes of exposure under the electron beam to partially cure. This locally heats the resin above 100°C , or well past the minimum viscosity temperature [12]. While μ CT may aid in characterizing incoming material quality, there remain an array of issues associated with the process such as material size limitations [13], material aspect ratios, and equipment cost.

Another less documented strategy involves substituting a more reactive trifunctional amine, specifically gaseous ammonia, to advance cure. This has been used on epoxy powders [14] and thin epoxy coating on animal fibres [15]. Rather than using gaseous ammonia at elevated temperatures, room temperature aqueous ammonium hydroxide is explored in this work as a potential means of stiffening epoxy prepreg in preparation for characterization.

2 METHOD

2.1 Characterization on the effects of an ammonium hydroxide soak

Several samples of AS4/8552-1 unidirectional (UD) prepreg, with a nominal fibre volume fraction of 57.42% [16], were left to soak at room temperature in an aqueous solution of 28 – 30% ACS grade ammonium hydroxide. A vacuum dry stage was employed to drive off any remnant water or ammonium hydroxide which would undergo a phase transition through a heating cycle and create artefacts in the data collection. In addition to a 0 hour soak and 0 hour vacuum dry control specimen, a test matrix, consisting of 0, 1, 4, 8, 12, 21, or 24 hour soak times with either 1 or 20 hour vacuum dry times, was used to prepare the modified samples. Each of the samples was a single ply thick to maximize the surface area to volume ratio in order to minimize concentration and/or cure gradients in the material. The samples were prepared so that each would have a sufficient amount of reactive material, approximately 5mg of epoxy, for testing in a modulated differential scanning calorimeter (MDSC).

A TA Instruments Discovery DSC was used to measure the thermal response of the modified prepreg. A heat-only MDSC cycle with an underlying $2 \frac{^{\circ}\text{C}}{\text{min}}$ ramp rate modulated by $\pm 0.318^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a frequency of $\frac{1}{60}$ Hz from -80°C to 300°C was used to generate thermograms, plots of heat flow as a function of temperature, along with plots of reversing specific heat capacity as a function of temperature. These temperature range, ramp rate, and modulation period parameters were chosen as they captured the initial glass transition temperature and the full exothermic reaction of the resin. Also, each parameter was consistent with previously published literature on characterizing Hexcel 8552 [17, 18].

Degree of cure was calculated using a heat of reaction comparison according to ASTM standard E2160-04 [19], restated in equation (1).

$$DC = \left(1 - \frac{H}{H_t}\right) \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where DC is the degree of cure, H is the normalized heat of reaction, and H_t is the total heat of reaction.

A sigmoidal baseline, with tangent and horizontal constraints on the lower and upper limits, respectively, was used to determine both the normalized heat of reaction for each trial as well as the total heat of reaction for the control sample.

The glass transition temperature was measured as the half-height temperature of the step change in reversing specific heat capacity [20].

Varying the ammonium hydroxide soak time in a thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA) was not feasible due to risk of contamination. Therefore, measurement of volumetric resin chemical shrinkage, α_{CS} , was determined by measuring the width of a large sample before and after the soak. Applying the reasonable assumption that cure shrinkage causes no change in length in the 1-direction and an equal amount in the transverse directions [21], then cure shrinkage can be determined using equation (2).

$$\alpha_{CS} = 2 \cdot \frac{L_f - L_o}{(1 - v_f) \cdot L_o} \quad (2)$$

where v_f is the fibre volume fraction, L_o is the initial length in the 2-direction, and L_f is the post-cure length in the 2-direction.

A sample was prepared using the full width of the UD prepreg roll, 305.6mm (12 $\frac{1}{32}$ "), and a length of 152.4mm (6"). The sample was measured using a meter stick and a Nikon Metrology coordinate measurement machine (CMM) with a XC65D non-contact laser scanning head. The laser scanning head required an opaque white talc powder to be applied on the surface.

2.2 In-plane misalignment characterization

Two single ply AS4/8552-1 samples, approximately 17cm long by 3cm wide, were removed from nominally the same position of a prepreg roll. One was subject to a 21 hour ammonium hydroxide soak followed by a 1 hour vacuum dry cycle while the other was cured according to MRCC, save the sample was cured in an oven and not an autoclave. Therefore only 1 atmosphere of pressure differential was applied rather than the MRCC 7.1 atmospheres. Autoclave pressures are mainly used to drive off porosity which has not been an issue for the small, single ply, laminates.

After their respective curing strategies had completed, the samples were cut at a nominal 5° angle in the 1-2 plane, mounted in a Buehler EpoKwick room temperature curing epoxy, ground, polished, and imaged using a Nikon Epiphot 300 optical microscope. Yurgartis's method [2] was used to determine the fibre alignment distributions. This method involves comparing the major and minor diameters, $d_{f,major}$ and $d_{f,minor}$, of ellipses which are generated as cylindrical fibres are sectioned at an angle. This angle, ω_f , between the fibre's direction and the cutting plane can be determined using equation (3). After accounting for bias in counting fibres with large misalignment angles, a distribution of in-plane fibre angles with respect to the cutting plane can be created.

$$\omega_f = \arcsin \frac{d_{f,minor}}{d_{f,major}} \quad (3)$$

3 RESULTS

3.1 Effect of the ammonium hydroxide soak on the thermal and chemical properties

Thermograms of the 13 different ammonium hydroxide soak and vacuum dry cases are plotted in Figure 2. Each of the thermograms feature at least one distinct exothermic peak with a discontinuity in the first derivative of the heat flow to the right of the maximum peaks. These discontinuities are likely the result of a degradation reaction rather than a curing reaction and were therefore chosen as the upper limits for the baseline determination.

Figure 2: Thermograms of ammonium hydroxide soaked and vacuum dried AS4/8552-1 prepreg. Exothermic heat flow is plotted as a positive value. (a) 1 hour vacuum dry. (b) 20 hour vacuum dry. (For interpretation of the figures with respect to legend and colour, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

The thermogram for the control sample was similar to the 0 hour ammonium hydroxide soak trials; however, it did not feature the high temperature discontinuity. Instead, a linear baseline from 40°C to 250°C was used to determine the total heat of reaction for 8552-1. H_t was calculated to be 590.67 J/g, well within one standard deviation, 597.89 ± 21.65 J/g, for the similar resin system, 8552, previously reported [17].

Figure 3 plots the evolution of degree of cure determined from the residual normalized heat of reaction. Nearly full conversion is attained after a 24 hour soak regardless of the vacuum dry time.

Figure 3: Degree of cure evolution due to varying lengths of ammonium hydroxide soak time.

The glass transition temperature increases from its initial 2.8°C to a maximum of 76.6°C. The samples prepared with a 1 hour vacuum dry showed only a minor increase, consistent with only the effect of the vacuum dry, for the first 4 hour soak in ammonium hydroxide. After the 4 hour period, the glass transition temperature increases logarithmically, plateauing near the 24 hour mark. Samples prepared with a 20 hour vacuum dry showed a logarithmic increase in glass transition temperature without any lag.

Figure 4: Glass transition temperature increase due to varying lengths of ammonium hydroxide soak time.

Plotting the cure rate as a function of cure displays the different reaction kinetics. Both the 1 hour and 20 hour vacuum dry conditions are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Cure rate as a function of degree of cure for a) 1 hour vacuum dry or b) 20 hour vacuum dry for c) various soak times

The 2-direction path length reduction, as read from the meter stick, was 0.1mm, resulting in a ammonium hydroxide soak volumetric cure shrinkage of 1.5%, well below the recorded thermal cure volumetric cure shrinkage of 4.94% [21]. Minor undulations of the prepreg surface after the soak did not allow the true 2-direction path length to be determined, as a result the 1.5% cure shrinkage is likely an upper estimate. The point cloud data, output from the CMM, was used to calculate the 2-direction path length using a 3D linear interpolation while holding constant the 2-direction value. Figure 6 shows the surface scan before the ammonium hydroxide soak. After a 33 hour soak in the ammonium hydroxide, the CMM recorded a 0.67% increase in length. This increase in path length can likely be attributed to the increased roughness observed in the post-soak talc surface and is doubtful to be truly representative of an expansion in the epoxy.

Figure 6: Surface profile of a single ply of AS4/8552-1 unidirectional prepreg prior to any modification.

Both distributions generated from the Yurgartis analysis show symmetric profiles with standard deviations of 1.08° and 1.57° for the ammonium hydroxide soak and the traditional thermal cure cycle samples, respectively. Both values were the distillation of approximately 30000 fibres, hence, confidence in their accuracy is high.

Figure 7: In-plane fibre angle distribution of AS4/8552-1. (a) After a 21 hour ammonium hydroxide soak followed by a 1 hour vacuum dry. (b) After a thermal cure cycle.

The main assumption required when applying the Yurgartis method is that the fibres are straight in the region they are cut; this assumption was not deemed inappropriate upon inspection of the micrographs as only a very small minority of the ellipses were distorted. Further, some error is generated as fibres with an actual angle less than the negative value of the cutting plane angle will contribute to the lower end of the distribution. This can be visualized in the asymmetry between the left and right tails of the distributions in Figure 7; however, this does not significantly impact the results.

4 DISCUSSION

Advancing degree of cure by exposing the specimens of AS4/8552-1 prepreg to aqueous ammonium hydroxide is a simple and effective technique. After 24 hours suspended in solution, the residual heat of reaction decreases to less than 10% of its initial value. This value is less than half the residual heat of reaction a typical AS4/8552 sample would retain after an MRCC. This implies most of the epoxides in the system have been consumed. As this reaction is occurring at room temperature, the added ammonium hydroxide must be reacting with the epoxides while the latent amines, DDS, have little contribution. This can be viewed in Figure 2, but very visible in Figure 5, as the speciation occurring due to the different soak

times. This speciation is visible as double peaks in the temperature-heat flow diagrams and the cure-cure rate diagrams of the 1 hour soak trial with a 1 hour vacuum dry and both 4 hour soak trials, 1 and 20 hour vacuum dry. Remnant, lower activation energy, ammonium hydroxide will react first creating its distinct exothermic peak. Before all of the first amine reactant has been consumed, the primary DDS/TGDDM reaction initiates. This can be seen by the first peak not decaying to the baseline before the beginning of the secondary peak. However, without the added heat from the MDSC, the DDS compounds will remain in the system without contributing to the growing macromolecule. As such, the macromolecule will be much less efficiently packed in its final state. Further, this ammonium hydroxide reaction is occurring at room temperature, hence the molecular spatial freedom is reduced, leading to a less efficient arrangement when compared to the traditional MRCC.

This decrease in density and arrangement efficiency is evident from the change in glass transition temperature. From the prepregs initial 2.8°C, the maximum glass transition temperature recorded was 76.6°C which is significantly lower than an MRCC glass transition temperature of 200°C.

Insufficient vacuum dry times also show a clear reduction in glass transition temperature. This can likely be attributed to the failure to remove water absorbed during the aqueous solution soak. Water will diffuse into the epoxy structure without bonding, further decreasing the molecular packing efficiency. With the macromolecule otherwise unchanged, this inefficiency creates a softer material as demonstrated by a decrease in glass transition temperature. This process is generally referred to as plasticization. While for all cases the glass transition temperature is lower than MRCC values, the ammonium soak technique is still a very valuable for characterization as it is still much higher than room temperature. This allows traditional characterization to be used without modification.

Without properly accounting for the effect of the cure cycle on fibre alignment characterization, improper values will be returned from post cure characterization. During a thermal cure cycle there are several concurrent events which would affect fibre misalignments. The aforementioned increase in temperature and resultant decrease in shear storage modulus creates a relaxation effect, the straightening out of initially misaligned fibres, during the heat up and hold before gelation. Simultaneously acting counter to this relaxation is the cure shrinkage which, with sufficient interaction between resin and fibre, will increase the degree of misalignments. Without accounting for these alterations, a post thermal cure analysis might erroneously return a standard deviation on fibre alignments of 1.57°. However, without decreasing the prepreg shear storage modulus and with a maximum $\frac{1}{3}$ the relative volumetric cure shrinkage, the initial prepreg standard deviation on fibre alignment is more accurately recorded as 1.08°. This disparity is very significant as the distributions show only 5.5% of the fibres falling outside of $\pm 2^\circ$ of the lamina 0° direction for the initial prepreg while 16.7% of fibres fall outside of $\pm 2^\circ$ for the post-thermal cure.

5 CONCLUSION

A simple, inexpensive, room temperature, ammonium hydroxide soak increases the glass transition temperature of an epoxy prepreg well beyond room temperature. These gains come with a fraction of the MRCC cure shrinkage and without the transient decrease in resin properties due to thermal cycling.

Traditional, well documented and robust, characterization techniques have been employed which clearly show a difference between a relatively unperturbed specimen and a thermally-cured specimen. It is therefore possible to more accurately quantify the state of the incoming prepreg with minimal effort and cost.

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